

BINO VA INSHOOTLARNI QURISH VA ISHLASH XAVFSIZLIGI” FMAQSAD VA VAZIFALAR.

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Kirish. Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2018-yil 31-iyul, 603-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan “O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Qurilish vazirligi to‘g‘risida”gi NIZOM da quriulish vazirligi o‘z vakolati doirasida quyidagilarni amalga oshiradi:

-binolar, inshootlar va ularning alohida yelementlariga bo‘lgan xavfsizlik talablarini, shuningdek, bino va inshootlarning yenergiya samaradorligini oshirish bo‘yicha chora-tadbirlarni ishlab chiqadi;

-shaharsozlik faoliyatida mahsulotlar, ishlar va xizmatlar xavfsizligiga qo‘yiladigan majburiy talablarga taalluqli texnik jihatdan tartibga solish sohasida ishlar bajarilishini ta‘minlaydi;

-arxitektura, loyihalash va qurilish sohasida malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashga tizimli asosda ko‘maklashishni ta‘minlaydi.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “O‘zbekiston Respublikasi qurilish sohasini modernizasiyalash, jadal va innovasion rivojlantirishning 2020—2025-yillarga mo‘ljallangan strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi farmoyish loyihasida ko‘rsatilganidek, O‘zbekistonda qurilish sohasini modernizasiyalash, jadal va innovasion rivojlantirishning asosiy yo‘nalishlari sifatida quyidagilar belgilangan:

-o‘qitishning zamonaviy va innovasion usullari qo‘llanishini hisobga olgan holda qurilish yo‘nalishidagi kadrlarni tayyorlash, qayta tayyorlash va malakasini oshirishni tashkil qilish tizimini takomillashtirish;

- qurilish obektlarida qurilish-montaj ishlarini bajarishda mehnat muhofazasi va xavfsizlik texnikasiga bo‘lgan talablarni kuchaytirish kabi dolzarb masalalar qo‘yilgan.

“Loyiha-qidiruv hamda qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlarining faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish, ular o‘rtasida sog‘lom raqobat muhitini shakllantirish maqsadida reyting tizimi yo‘lga qo‘yilayapti. Bu bilan loyihalovchi va quruvchining ishi bino foydalanishga topshirilib, barcha yutuq hamda kamchiliklarlar yuzaga chiqqach yemas, balki qurilish-montaj jarayonida baholab boriladi. Bu to‘g‘risida 2020 yil 9 noyabrda Vazirlar Mahkamasining 699-sonli “Loyiha-qidiruv va qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlari reytingini hisoblash va yuritish tartibini joriy yetish chora tadbirlari

to'g'risida" gi qarori qabul qilindi. Ushbu me'yoriy hujjat asosida Loyiha-qidiruv va qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlari reytingini hisoblash va yuritish tartibi to'g'risida nizom ham tasdiqlandi."

Yendi qurilishlarning yelectron bazasi tuzilib tashkilotlarning reytingi ochiq va oshkoro tarzda baholanib boriladi.

Ushbu ma'ruza matnlari Respublikamizda qurilish sohasidagi islohotlarni amalga oshirish uchun "Bino, inshootlarni qurish va ishlash xavfsizligi" fanidan 5860100-"Hayotiy faoliyat xavfsizligi" ta'lim yo'nalishi bo'yicha malakali bakalavrlar tayyorlash uchun mo'ljallangan muhim manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Kapital qurilish Respublikamiz xalq xo'jaligida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Har qanday davlatning material-texnik bazasini yaratish kapital qurilishsiz tassavur qilib bo'lmaydi.

Qurilish konstruksiyalari - har qanday bino va sun'iy inshootlarni qurish, turarjoy binolari, jamoat, sanoat va qishloq xo'jalik binolari, ko'priklar, katta hajmli imoratlar, quvurlar va inshootlarning asosi hisoblanadi. Bino va inshootni qurish uchun sarflangan xarajatlarning asosiy qismi konstruksiyalarga to'g'ri keladi.

Hozirgi kunda amalga oshirilayotgan katta hajmdagi kapital qurilishlar, qurilish konstruksiyalaridan samarali foydalanish rivojining juda tez jadallashuviga turtki bo'ldi - konstruksiyalarning turlari va ulardan tayyorlanadigan xomashyolar to'xtovsiz takomillashib bormoqda. Shu boisdan ularni hisoblash, loyihalash va tiklash usullari ham takomillashtirilmoqda.

Qurilish konstruksiyalarini hisoblashdan maqsad qurilishning samaradorligini oshirish, uning konstruktiv sxemalarini ixchamlashtirish va konstruksiyalarni tiplashtirish asosida, iloji boricha ko'proq tayyorligini oshirish bo'lsa, ikkinchisi - bu imoratlarni raqobatbardosh, yuqori sifatli, shinam va vazifaviy qulay bo'lishini ta'minlashdir. Shu tufayli mexanizatsiyalashtirilgan va avtomatlashtirilgan texnologik arayonlarni qo'llash bilan bir qatorda qurilish maydonchalarida bajariladigan ishlarga keng imkoniyatlar ochib berildi. Qurilish konstruksiyalari ularda qo'llanadigan materiallariga ko'ra metalli (odatda po'latdan), g'isht-toshli, betonli va temirbetonli, yog'och yoki plastmassali konstruksiyalarga bo'linadi.

XVI-XVII asrlarda bino va inshootlarni qurishda dastlab bog'lovchi unsur sifatida foydalanildi, keyinchalik XVIII asrdan boshlab metallni qurilish konstruksiyasi sifatida qo'llaniladi. Birinchi cho'yan ko'priki XVIII asrda (Angliyada 1779 yili va 1784 yili Rossiyada) quriladi.

XIX asrda muayyan shakldagi metall buyumlarning ishlab chiqarilishi qurilishda ishlatiladigan unsurlarini oqilona kesimlarini hosil qilinishiga sabab bo'ldi. Po'lat konstruksiyalarining unsurlarini yig'ishda payvandlashni qo'llanilishi konstruksiyalarni ishlab

chiqarishda mehnat sarfini ancha kamayishiga va qurilishda keng miqyosda qo'llanilishiga olib keldi.

XIX asrning o'rtalarida yangi material - temirbeton paydo bo'ldi, unda beton va metallning maqbul mutanosiblikda ishlatiladi. O'sha davrda konstruksiyalarni hisobi paydo bo'ldi va rivojlantirildi. Konstruksiyalarni hisoblashning ilmiy usullari doimo rivojlantirilib kelinmoqda.

Qurilish-montaj ishlarini xavfsiz olib borish uchun montaj ishlari mutaxassislari bino va inshootlarni asosiy hajmiy-rejaviy va konstruksiyaviy yechimlarini, ularda qo'llaniladigan metall va temirbeton materiallarining fizik va mexanik xususiyatlarini bilishi, konstruksiyalarning unsurlarini hisobiy sxemalarini va ularning zo'riqish holatini montaj jarayonida va ulardan foydalanish davrida aniq tassovur eta bilishlari hamda, uncha murakkab bo'lmagan konstruksiyalarning unsurlarni hisoblay olishlari kerak.

Oxirgi o'n yilliklarda sanoatning taraqqiy etishi davomida Respublikamizda qurilish konstruksiyalari miqyosida texnikaviy o'sish kuzatildi. Sanoat bazasining kundan-kunga rivojlanishi, materiallar va ashyolarning mustahkamlik xususiyati ortmoqda, yangi zamonaviy kurinishdagi konstruksiyalar chiqarilmoqda (sendvich panellar, KNAUF materiallari, turli xil suvoq qorishmalar va qoplamalar va h.k.), ularning zavod sharoitda tayyorlanishi oshmoqda.

Temirbeton va fazoviy-strukturaviy konstruksiyalar keng miqyosda qo'llanilmoqda.

Fanning maqsadi qurilish konstruksiyalarini hisoblash va konstruksiyalash bo'yicha malaka hosil qilish, meyyoriy hujjatlardan va boshqa texnik adabiyotlardan foydalanish. Bino va inshootlar loyihalanishida har xil konstruksiyalarni qollash va konstrktiv echimlami, konstruksiyalar tizimi asoslari bilan qurollantirish, konstruksiyalami qo'llashda mantiqiy fikrlash, tasavur etish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish, bino va inshootlarni avariya holatlami oldindan belgilash va ulami bartaraf qilish chora-tadbirlariga tayyorgarlik ishlarini bajarish mahoratiga ega bo'lish.

Fanning vazifasi Respublikamizda va xorijda bunyod etilayotgan, yangi qurilish yo'nalishlari bilan tanishtirish, qurilish materiallari hozirgi zamon talablariga javob berishi uchun davlatimizda standartlash, sertifikatlash va metrologiya asoslari, ishlabchiqarish sohasidagi fan va texnika yutuqlari, bino, inshootlarni xavfsiz ekspluatasiya sharoitlarini ta'minlash haqida tasawurga ega bo'lishi, binolami qurish va barpo etishda loyihasidan foydalana olishi, arxitektura-qurilish jarayonida atrof-muhitni muhofazalash ko'nikma va malakalarini hosil qilishdir.

Metall konstruksiyalari materialning yuqori darajada mustahkamligi evaziga kam xussiy massasiga ega. Ularni maxsus zavodlarda tayyorlanishi va qurilish maydonida montaj qilinishi

uncha katta mehnat xarajatlarini talab qilmaydi. Ammo ularning zanglashga moyilligi foydalanish davrida esa, davriy ravishda bo'yash ishlariga ko'p xarajatlarni talab etadi.

REFERENCES

1. Dustkobilovich R. O., Laylo A. Types of modern lectures in higher education, technology of their design and organization //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 12-1 (157). – С. 41-46.
2. Рахимов О. Д., Манзаров Ю. Х., Ашурова Л. Ўзбекистон олий таълим тизимида дастлабки форсайт тадқиқотлар //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 4 (101). – С. 16-22.
3. Rakhimov O. D., Kh M. Y., Ashurova L. Initial foresight studies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Modern education (Uzbekistan).–2021. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 101. – С. 16-22.
4. Рахимов О. Д., Эшмухамедов Л. М., Ашурова Л. МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМНИ РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ: Рахимов Октябр Дусткабилович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси профессори Эшмухамедов Латиф Махмаюсуфович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти Ашурова Лайло, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 6.
5. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.
6. Rakhimov O., Ashurova L., Artikbekova F. Hydraulic transport in small livestock farms //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 274. – С. 03003.
7. Rakhimov O. D., Ashurova L. THE MAIN FACTORS AND CRITERIA OF QUALITY EDUCATION //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 31. – С. 163-169.
8. Ashurova L. METHODOLOGY OF USING TELECOMMUNICATION STUDY PROJECTS IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 135-140.

9. Ashurova L. ON THE TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN STUDENTS //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 23. – С. 294-298.
10. Rakhimov O. D., Sh F. S., Ashurova L. Foresight as a technology for forecasting the development of the use of digital technologies in the higher education sector of Uzbekistan //The phenomenon of market economy: from the origins to the present day. Development institutions and information technologies in innovative solutions. – 2022. – С. 167-175.
11. Husanovich S. B., Ravshanovich B. Z., Laylo A. ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION MODELS //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 11 (59). – С. 86-90.
12. Рахимов О. Д., Файзиева Ш. Ш., Ашурова Л. Форсайт как технология прогнозирования развития применения цифровых технологий в секторе высшего образования Узбекистана //Феномен рыночного хозяйства: от истоков до наших дней. Институты развития и информационные технологии в инновационных решениях. – 2022. – С. 167-175.
13. Shomurotov B. H., Boyirov Z. R., Ashurova L. ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION MODELS //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 11. – С. 86-90.
14. Ashurova L., Uralov M. BINO VA INSHOOTLAR XAVFSIZLIGI //FANINI O 'QITISHNING BA'ZI JIHATLARI//Interpretation and researches.–2024.
15. Ashurova L., Uralov M. «BINO VA INSHOOTLAR XAVFSIZLIGI» FANINI O 'QITISHNING BA'ZI JIHATLARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
16. Ashurova L. ZILZILA, KELIB CHIQUISH SABABLARI VA OQIBATLARI //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 423-431.
17. Ashurova L. FIRES IN TECHNOSPHERE AND PRINCIPLES OF PROTECTION AGAINST THEM //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 20. – С. 81-86.
18. Laylo A. ISHLAB CHQARISH XONALARI HAVOSINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH UCHUN KONDITSIONER USKUNASINING ISHINI QIYOSIY TAHLIL QILISH VA UNI MODELLASHTIRISH //Sanoatda raqamli texnologiyalar/Цифровые технологии в промышленности. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 184-192.
19. ASHUROVA L. ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ Учредители: Олимп. – С. 41-46.

20. Маматов Ф. М., Шодмонов Г. Д. Обоснование конструктивной схемы комбинированного агрегата для подготовки почвы к посеву бахчевых //European research. – 2018. – №. 1 (35). – С. 10-14.
21. Murtozevich M. F., Halilovich M. S., Dustmurodovich S. G. Dump ripper for soil protection from water erosion //European science review. – 2018. – №. 7-8. – С. 245-246.
22. Мирзаев Б. С., Мардонов Ш. Х., Шодмонов Г. Д. О качестве рыхления почвы рыхлителем с рабочими органами наклонного типа //European research. – 2018. – №. 1 (35). – С. 15-18.
23. Mamatov F. M., Mardonov S. H., Shodmonov G. D. DUMP RIPPER FOR SOIL PROTECTION FROM WATER EROSION //European Science Review. – 2018. – №. 7-8. – С. 245-246.
24. Чуянов Д. Ш. и др. ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНЛАРИ ЭКИШ УЧУН ТУПРОҚНИ ТАЙЁРЛАЙДИГАН КОМБИНАЦИЯЛАШГАН АГРЕГАТ КОРПУСЛАРИНИНГ ПАРАМЕТРЛАРИ //Инновацион технологиялар. – 2021. – №. Спецвыпуск 1. – С. 146-150.
25. Шодмонов Г. Д., ўғли Хидиров М. Қ. АВТОТРАНСПОРТ ЧИҚИНДИ ГАЗЛАРИ ЗАРАРЛИЛИГИНИ КАМАЙТИРИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ УСУЛЛАРИ //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 18. – С. 140-147.
26. Чуянов Д. и др. КОМБИНАЦИЯЛАШГАН АГРЕГАТ ЮМШАТКИЧЛАРИНИНГ ЎЗАРО ЖОЙЛАШИШИНИ АСОСЛАШ //Innovatsion texnologiyalar. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 61-63.
27. Shodmonov G., Xidirov M., Boymurodov S. AVTOMOBILLARNING ELEKTR VA ELEKTRON JIHOZLARINI DIAGNOSTIKALASH //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 20. – С. 57-61.
28. Chuyanov D. et al. Parameters of slit for embedding manure in soil for melon crops //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 401. – С. 04048.
29. Чуянов Д. Ш., Шодмонов Г. Д. ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ОПТИМАЛЬНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ СТАЛКИВАТЕЛЯ НАВОЗА //Вестник науки и образования. – 2023. – №. 12 (143)-2. – С. 5-9.
30. Чуянов Д. Ш., Шодмонов Г. Д. ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ ЩЕЛКОВАТЕЛЯ ДЛЯ ЗАДЕЛКИ НАВОЗА //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 1017-1023.

31. Dostmurodovich G. S. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF FUNDS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH OUTPUT. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 57-61.
32. Dostmurodovich G. S. LABOR PROTECTION WHEN WORKING AT HEIGHTS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 31-38.
33. Shodmonov G. “FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR VA FUQARO MUHOFAZASI” FANING MAQSAD VA VAZIFALARI //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
34. Чуянов Д. Ш. и др. Полиз экинлари етиштиришда тупрокка ишлов бериш ва экишнинг янги усули //Инновацион технологиялар. – 2021. – №. Спецвыпуск 2. – С. 53-56.
35. Чуянов Д. Ш. и др. ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНЛАРИ ЕТИШТИРИШ УЧУН ЭНЕРГИЯ-РЕСУРСТЕЖАМКОР ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ВА МАШИНА //Инновацион технологиялар. – 2020. – №. Спецвыпуск. – С. 78-82.
36. Маматов Ф. М., Чуянов Д. Ш., Шодмонов ҒД Э. М. И. Далаларни полиз экинлари экиш учун тайёрлайдиган комбинациялашган агрегатнинг параметрларини асослаш //Innovatsion texnologiyalar.–Қарши. – 2018. – №. 4. – С. 44-48.
37. Mirzaev B. et al. Parameters of the soil-holding part of the slurry spreader //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 383. – С. 04016.
38. Chuyanov D. S., Mamatov F. M., Shodmonov G. D. Main parameters of manure sealer //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 401. – С. 04031.
39. Shodmonov G. D., Xidirov MQ Avtotransport chiqindi gazlari zararliligini kamaytirishning zamonaviy usullari //International conference on innovative development of education. – 2022. – Т. 18. – С. 140-147.
40. Mamatov F., Karimov A., Shodmonov G. Study on the parameters of bars of the potato digger ploughshare //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 434. – С. 03012.
41. Chuyanov D., Shodmonov G. Energy-saving technology and machinery for growing melons //International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 1-7.
42. Shodmonov G. D. et al. MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI FANINING RIVOJLANISH TARIXI VA BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN O ‘ZARO BOG ‘LIQLIGI //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 149-153.

43. Chuyanov D. et al. Traction resistance of the combined machine plough //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – Т. 264. – С. 04036.
44. Mamatov F. et al. Potato digger with a digging workpart of the " Paraplaw" type //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 365. – С. 04021.
45. Murtozevich M. F. et al. New technology and combined machine for preparing soil for sowing gourds //European science review. – 2018. – №. 1-2. – С. 234-236.
46. Chuyanov D. et al. Soil preparation machine parameters for the cultivation of cucurbitaceous crops //IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. – IOP Publishing, 2020. – Т. 883. – №. 1. – С. 012122.
47. Mirzaev B. et al. Combined machine for preparing soil for cropping of melons and gourds //IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. – IOP Publishing, 2019. – Т. 403. – №. 1. – С. 012158.

48. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 758-773.
49. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects //JournalNX. – С. 301-308.
50. Dildora X., Sirojiddin M. O ‘zbekiston respublikasi hududida seysmoaktiv hududlar va zilzilaning xavfliligi //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2024. – С. 167-172.
51. ЎҒЛИ Р. Х. Ф., СИРОЖИДДИН М. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10.
52. O‘G‘LI M. S. H. ANALYSIS OF “MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING.” //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
53. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.

54. Rakhimov O. D., Muradov S. H. Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques //European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS). – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 80-86.
55. Muradov S. H. o ‘g ‘li, & Zayniyev, UU o ‘g ‘li.(2023). PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 116-119.
56. Muradov S. ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROFITS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1239-1245.
57. МУРАДОВ С. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ОХРАНА ТРУДЫ НА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ КОРЕИ //ХӨДӨЛМӨР, НИЙГМИЙН ХАРИЛЦАА СУДЛАЛ. – 2023. – С. 242-247.
58. СИРОЖИДДИН М. РАЖАБОВ ХУРШИД ФАХРИДДИН ЎҒЛИ. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 10. – С. 27.
59. Husan o‘g‘li M. S., Utkir o‘g‘li Z. U. PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 11.
60. Мурадов С. Определение отдыха и отпусков на основании нового трудового кодекса //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 26. – С. 17-21.
61. Muradov S. H. Safarov Sh. O ‘. MEHNAT SHAROITLARI VA MUHITINI “KAIZEN” USULI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI //PAXTA TOZALASH, TO ‘QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT SOHALARINING TEXNOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. – 2023. – С. 90-92.
62. Sirojiddin M. Mehanatni muhofaza qilishning tashkiliy-psixologik asoslaridagi mavjud muammolar //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – С. 133-137.
63. Sirojiddin M. Mehnat sharoitlari va muhitini “kaizen” usuli yordamida takomillashtirishning innovatsion yechimlari //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – С. 249-253.
64. Muradov S. H. o ‘g ‘li, & Egamov, DS o ‘g ‘li.(2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN

- HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 340-342.
65. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 1142-1152.
66. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasida yuk ortish va tushirish ishlaridagi yukchilar uchun ishlarning xavfsizligi kategori va qoidalari tahlili //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 232-242.
67. Sirojiddin M. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 243-248.
68. Sirojiddin M. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 146-150.
69. Sirojiddin M. Xavfli sanoat korxonalarida ishchilarni xavfli gaz va zaxarli moddalar ta’siridan himoya qilishga qaratilgan inovatsion yechimlar //Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari. – 2023. – C. 402-405.
70. Muradov S. CONSTRUCTION-INSTALLATION ISHLARIDA KUTARAMA KRANLARDAN USE FUNDAMENTAL SECURITY OF SUPPLY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 786-792.
71. СИРОЖИДДИН М. НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 167-177.
72. Raximov O. D. Muradov SH Sanoat korxonalarini rahbari va mutaxassislarini mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha o‘qitish va bilimlarini sinovdan o‘tkazishni raqamlashtirish //INTELLEKT. MONOGRAFIYA. – 2023.
73. O‘G‘LI M. S. H. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 26. – C. 8-16.

74. Muradov S. ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 493-501.
75. Muradov S. Ishlab chiqarishdagi avariyalarni o'rganish va tahlil qilish //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 16. – С. 474-477.
76. СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер М. Каршинский инженерноэкономический институт кафедра «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан.(2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo //НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ.
77. Мурадов С. PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF USING LIFTING CRANES IN CONSTRUCTION-ASSEMBLY WORKS //MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 933-939.
78. Husan o'g'li M. S. Sanoat korxonalari rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo'yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati //Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. – 2023. – Т. 10. – №. 26. – С. 180-183.
79. Muradov S., Xujaqulov A., Eshmuxamedov L. ORGANIZING TRAINING ON THE CAUSES OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTION AT THE FOCUS OF INJURY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 247-264.
80. Muradov S., Usmonov H. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXIY BOSQICHLARINI O'RGANISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
81. Muradov S. CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 455-463.
82. Muradov S. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 473-484.
83. Muradov S. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WORKING ACCIDENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 444-454.
84. Muradov S. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 485-492.
85. Sirojiddin M. KTZM QO 'LLANILADIGAN OBYEKTlardagi AVARIYADA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH. – 2024.

86. O'G E. L. A. A. et al. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11.
87. Husan o'g'li M. S., Shavkat o'g'li E. D. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – C. 11-17.
88. Muradov S. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ORGANIZING THE EXAMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION OF MANAGERS AND SPECIALISTS OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 805-817.
89. Muradov S. ANALYSIS OF JOB SAFETY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR LOADING AND UNLOADING WORKERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 788-804.
90. Muradov S. DEFINITION OF REST AND LEAVES BASED ON THE NEW LABOR CODE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 774-787.
91. Muradov S. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE RARE DISEASES SUCH AS PLAGUE AND YELLOW FEVER //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 703-728.
92. Sirojiddin M. MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI SOHASIDAGI MAQSABLARNING IQTISODIY TAHLILI. – 2024.
93. Muradov S. EPISOTOTIC SITUATIONS, THEIR PREVENTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 831-851.
94. Muradov S. CAUSES, CHARACTERISTICS AND ACTIONS OF THE POPULATION IN THE FOCUSES OF DAMAGE OF EMERGENCIES OF A MAN-GENIC CHARACTER //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 729-744.
95. Sultonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 109-115.
96. Muradov S. et al. EMERGENCY EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, EPIZOOTIC AND EPIPHYTOTIC SITUATIONS. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT

- CAUSE INFECTIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 281-318.
97. Muradov S. et al. STANDARDS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS FOR PRESSURE CABINETS, APPARATUS AND GAS EQUIPMENT //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 159-180.
98. Husan ogli M. S., Hamidulla o'g'li X. X. Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi.(2021). NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – T. 2. – C. 28-30.
99. Muradov S. et al. STUDY OF THE HISTORICAL STAGES OF THE SCIENCE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 350-365.
100. Muradov S. et al. CHECKING KNOWLEDGE OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 386-400.
101. Muradov S. et al. MOVEMENT OF CHICTONIC PLATES, ORIGIN OF EARTHQUAKES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 401-415.
102. Muradov S. et al. MAIN CONTENT AND COMPONENT PARTS OF THE SCIENCE" SAFETY OF CONSTRUCTION OF BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS" //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 335-349.
103. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SECURITY CATEGORY AND RULES FOR CARRIERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 366-385.
104. Muradov S. et al. ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDINGS AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 257-280.
105. Muradov S. et al. STABILITY CALCULATION OF LOAD LIFT VEHICLES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 205-234.
106. Muradov S. et al. CONTENT AND ESSENCE OF THE LAW AND LEGAL DOCUMENTS ON THE PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION AND TERRITORIES FROM EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 168-204.
107. Muradov S. et al. CAUSES OF NATURAL EMERGENCIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 92-130.

108. Muradov S. et al. ANALYSIS OF SAFETY REQUIREMENTS OF EQUIPMENT WORKING UNDER HIGH PRESSURE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 131-167.
109. Qizi S. M. A. et al. O ‘QUV BINOLARI VA O ‘QUV MARKAZLARINI RANG YECHIMINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAMDA SUN’IY INTELLEKT ORQALI LOYIHALASH //Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 325-332.
110. Qizi S. M. A., Namazovna S. D. JAMOAT BINOLARI VA O ‘QUV MARKAZLARI UCHUN TASVIRIY SAN’AT VA RANG YECHIMINI LOYIHALASHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O ‘RNI //Raqamli iqtisodiyot (Цифровая экономика). – 2024. – №. 6. – С. 333-340.
111. Muradov S. et al. NATURAL EMERGENCIES, INFECTIOUS DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 416-441.
112. Мурадов С., Каримов Б., Сиддиқова М. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 600-618.
113. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARNING VUJUDGA KELISHI SABABLARI, VA FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARDA HARAKAT QILISHGA O ‘RGATISHNI TASHKIL ETISH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 554-573.
114. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHDA YUK KO ‘TARISH VOSITALARINI MUSTAHKAMLIKKA HISOBLASH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 636-655.
115. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR VA ULARNING TURLARI, TABIIY TUSDAGI FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLAR //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 656-680.
116. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA O ‘TA YUQORI BOSIM OSTIDA ISHLOVCHI USKUNLARNING XAVFSIZLIK TALABLARI TAXLILI TEXNIK ASOSLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 681-703.
117. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. KIMYOVIY AVARIYA HOLATINI BAHOLASH VA TAXLIL QILISH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5.

118. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 774-793.
119. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. KUCHLI TA'SIR ETUVCHI ZAHARLI MODDALAR AVARIYALARIDA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5.
120. Muradov S., Karimov B., Asatilla M. MAMURIY BINOLAR VA ULARNING TAVSIFLANISHI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5.
121. Мурадов С., Каримов Б., Сиддиқова М. ОТПУСКОВ НА ОСНОВАНИИ НОВОГО ТРУДОВОГО КОДЕКСА //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 619-635.
122. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 794-808.
123. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARINING MEXANIK XOSSALARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 144-164.
124. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARINING TUZILISHI VA TASNIFI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 98-121.
125. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. QURILISH ASHYOLARI TARKIBINI ILMIY ASOSLASH USULLARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 122-143.
126. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF ACCIDENTS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 16-31.
127. Muradov S., Siddiqova M., Karimov B. PARTICULARLY DANGEROUS INFECTIONS THAT CAUSE CONTAGIOUS AND COMMON DISEASES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 32-64.
128. Muradov S., Karimov B., Siddiqova M. FAVQULODDA VAZIYATLARDA TIZIMIGA DOIR QONUNCHILIK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 574-599.
129. Muradov S., Karimov B., Asatilla M. “BINO VA INSHOOTLARNI XAVFSIZLIGI” FANINING ASOSIY MAZMUNI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 809-824.

130. Рахимов О. АЙРИМ ХОРИЖИЙ ДАВЛАТЛАР ТАЖРИБАСИДА НОТАРИАЛ ФАОЛИЯТНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ВА НАЗОРАТНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.
131. Dustkabilovich R. O. THE EFFECT OF THE APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS.
132. Рахимов О. Д. Исследование процесса подачи кормосмесей пониженной влажности коловратным насосом на малых свинофермах. – 1992.
133. ТРЕГУБ Л. И., РАХИМОВ О. Д., ПРАВАТОВ Н. М. Установка для подачи влажных кормов. – 1993.
134. Dustkabilovich R. O. NECESSITY OF LIVE MODERN LECTURES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND ITS TYPES //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 10 (58). – С. 65-69.
135. Dustkabilovich R. O. et al. Description of pedagogical technology and problematic teaching technology //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 2 (147). – С. 59-62.
136. Рахимов О. Д. ИНТЕРНЕТ-ОБУЧЕНИЕ МУЗЫКЕ //Рекомендовано к печати Ученым советом Института психологии имени ГС Костюка НАПН Украины (Протокол № 14 от 28 декабря 2020). – 2020. – С. 412.
137. РАХИМОВ О. Д., МАНЗАРОВ Ю. Х., АШУРОВА Л. PRIMARY FORESIGHT RESEARCH IN THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 16-22.
138. Рахимов О. Д., Рахимова Д. О. Форсайт исследование по прогнозированию развития цифровизации высшего образования Республики Узбекистан. – 2021.
139. Рахимов О. Д., Ашурова Л. ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ИНТЕРАКТИВ УСЛУБЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ //RESEARCH AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – С. 332.
140. Rakhimov O., Nuriddinova S. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF APPLYING PROJECT METHOD TECHNOLOGY IN INDEPENDENT STUDY OF THE SUBJECT OF BIOLOGY //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 375-380.
141. Dustkabilovich R. O. MASOFAVIY TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI TASNIFI //International journal of scientific researchers (IJSR) INDEXING. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2.
142. Рахимов О. Д., Рахматов М. И. ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОХРАНОЙ ТРУДА НА

- ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ //Феномен рыночного хозяйства: от истоков до наших дней. Трансформация экономических систем в контексте турбулентного развития. – 2023. – С. 246-253.
143. OD R. et al. Methodology of Education of Specialists in Industrial Enterprises using for Site Technology on the Effect of Electricity on the Human Body. – 2023.
144. Raximov O. D. GLOBALLASHUV DAVRIDA TA'LIM TIZIMI MUAMMOLARI //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 10-16.
145. Raximov O. D. i dr. Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari //Т.:“Fan va texnologiya nashriyoti.–2013.
146. Шодиева М., Рахимов О. Д. Ўқитувчилар малака ошириш тизимида таълим сифатини таъминлашда ўқув-услугий мажмуаларнинг ўрни //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 24-28.
147. Азаренкова Г. М. и др. ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНО-ВОСПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ФОРМАЦИОННОЙ РАЗВИЛКИ: ПРИНЦИПЫ, ФОРМЫ, ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ. – 2021.
148. Рахимов О. Д., Чоршанбиев З. Э. Форсайт как инструмент прогнозирования применения информационно-цифровой технологии в высшем образовании республики Узбекистана //Феномен рыночного хозяйства: от истоков до наших дней. Синтез цифровых технологий и инновационных решений. – 2021. – С. 326-335.
149. Raximov O. D. Manzarov Yu. X., Ashurova L. O 'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida dastlabki forsayt tadqiqotlar //Sovremennoye obrazovaniye (Uzbekistan).–2021. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 101. – С. 16-22.
150. Anisimov K. V. et al. Phenomenon of market economy: business concepts of innovations in theoretical and practical solutions. – 2022.